

Guaranteed Active Constraints Enforcement on Point Cloud-approximated Regions for Surgical Applications

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Abstract—In this work, a passive physical human-robot interaction (pHRI) controller is proposed to intraoperatively ensure that sensitive tissues will not be damaged by the robot’s tool. The proposed scheme uses the point cloud of the restricted region’s surface as constraint definition and Artificial Potential fields for constraint enforcement. The controller is proven to be passive with respect to the interaction force and to guarantee constraint satisfaction in all cases. The proposed methodology is experimentally validated by the kinesthetic guidance of a KUKA LWR4+ robot’s end-effector driving a virtual slave KUKA in the vicinity of a 3D point-cloud of a kidney and its adjacent vessels.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation

In recent years, robot-assisted surgery has achieved widespread surgical application, enabling surgeons to perform complex and intricate tasks. Human-robot collaboration schemes are used for performing these tasks, such as telemanipulation [1] resulting, however, to a significant loss of the surgeon’s sensing perception (haptic or visual) compared to traditional surgeries [2]. Additionally, telemanipulation systems alone, are unable to provide any intelligent assistance to the surgeon, so their accuracy and precision is ultimately limited by the accuracy and precision of the human operator, even in perfectly designed telemanipulators (master-slave). This implies that the human-robot collaboration can lead to undesired results during surgery, such as serious damage of delicate tissues or organs. A proposed solution for this problem is the incorporation of Active Constraints (AC)/Virtual Fixtures (VF) [3] into the teleoperation’s control scheme, which reduces the risk of damaging adjacent tissues by preventing the motion of the robot within forbidden and sensitive areas and by providing intraoperative haptic feedback to the surgeon [4].

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B. Related Work

Active constraints are enforced via control schemes providing force feedback from virtual environments. They were firstly introduced in tele-robotic manipulation [5], [6] and have been utilized in surgical [7], [8], [9], [10], industrial [11], [12], or even in underwater robotic tasks [13]. They encourage motion inside a constraint region by acting repulsively away from forbidden regions, thus avoiding obstacles [14], further assisting the user in following a prespecified path [15]. They have also been used in region reaching control methods, which is a generalization of the set point control problem [16], [17], [18].

In surgery, active constraints can be placed around delicate tissue regions, preventing the surgeon from damaging them. Recent works on active constraint enforcement on surgical applications can be classified into two different approaches: these which focus on the dissipative behaviour of the robot and those which focus on the active enforcement of the constraints on the robot using energy-storing methods like artificial potential fields [19]. One of the most seminal works of the former category is presented in [8], in which a dissipative control scheme is proposed for complete pose control, employing energy redirection for increased task accuracy. However, the approach does not guarantee constraint satisfaction, which is one of the main objectives of our work. In contrast, as we have proved in [20], constraint enforcement via artificial potential fields is guaranteed when the constraint is defined analytically.

Proposed methods in robotic surgery incorporate different ideas like artificial potential fields, point clouds [21] and a virtual object (proxy/god-object) [22], [23] or a combination of them for producing a repulsive force [24]. Leibbrandt *et. al.* [24], proposes a method which uses point clouds as constraints and produce a repulsive force on the tool. Although, this work considers the whole tool mass, it lacks a proper stability analysis; moreover, the proposed discrete forces are mathematically undefined when the tool is exactly on the constraint. In [25], which is an improvement of [21], the authors combine the idea of the proxy object, commonly used in haptic interfaces for virtual environment [23], with the use of a point cloud by having spheres on each point and the proxy object staying on these spherical boundaries, when the constraint’s surface is violated. This method calculates the repulsive force on the haptic device as a spring force between the end-effector and the proxy.

C. Contributions

This work extends our stability and non constraint violation results of [20] when the restricted area is defined by a point cloud rather than analytically. The analysis is provided for the surgical tool tip; extensions for the whole tool mass are also given and experimentally validated. The proposed active constraint control law is proved to guarantee for the first time to our knowledge that the constraints are never violated by the tool tip and that the closed loop system is passive and its state bounded. Experimental results validate on-line constraint enforcement and real-time performance for the whole tool mass.

In the remainder of this paper, we first present, in Section II, the proposed methodology and the proposed controller's stability analysis. Then, in Section III, we present the experimental results on a use case involving a kidney to be operated and its adjacent vessels as constrained region and, finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section IV.

II. THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this section, the active constraints enforcement problem considered in this work is formulated, followed by the presentation of the proposed controller for the tool point, its stability analysis and its extension to the whole tool body. For the constraints representation, 3D point clouds are utilized.

A. Problem Formulation

Consider the case in which a human operator can move the robot in 3D-space by exerting forces on its end-effector via pHRI, by either kinesthetic guidance or using a haptic device in a master-slave setup, in which the slave robot's end-effector is guided by the forces exerted in the master haptic device. Consider a restricted region within the workspace of the robot, $\mathcal{O} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$, which should not be violated by the robot's end-effector, such as organ surfaces or delicate tissue structures, which should not be damaged. Let $\partial\mathcal{O}$ be the boundary of \mathcal{O} , which is assumed to be approximated by a finite set of points $\mathcal{O}_s \subset \partial\mathcal{O}$. If $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the position of the robot's end-effector during operation, our objective is the robot to actively resist the human operator in a way such that the end-effector never enters the restricted region, i.e., $\mathbf{p}(t) \notin \mathcal{O}$, for all $t \in [0, \infty)$, by exerting a repulsive force. This implies that the robot will not penetrate the constrained region's surface $\partial\mathcal{O}$. Additionally, consider the allowed region \mathcal{A} , in which the human operator can move the robot without any restriction from the active constraints (total absence of AC repulsive force) and hence \mathcal{O} and \mathcal{A} are disjoint sets. Similarly to the above, we assume a finite set of points \mathcal{A}_s which approximates the boundary $\partial\mathcal{A}$ of \mathcal{A} .

In this study, we assume that the surgical environment is provided as a point cloud from an endoscopic camera held by another arm, from which the operator selects a subset of the points as the restricted region \mathcal{O}_s and a subset of the points as the allowed region \mathcal{A}_s . Furthermore, we assume that the points belonging to \mathcal{O}_s and \mathcal{A}_s , are expressed in the robot's base coordinate system by appropriate transformations from the camera's frame.

B. The Methodology for the tool point

The approximation of the constrained region's surface by a finite set of points \mathcal{O}_s , results in an empty space between them. In order to compensate for the empty space, we create spheres, with radius d_c centered at each point of the \mathcal{O}_s . Let $\rho \in \mathbb{R}^+$ be the density of \mathcal{O}_s in points per cm^3 . Then the side of a cube which includes one point is $\frac{1}{\sqrt[3]{\rho}}$ and by selecting spheres with radius $d_c = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\sqrt[3]{\rho}}$ we can guarantee that these empty spaces are covered (fig. 1). Notice that the radius d_c depends on the density of \mathcal{O}_s , which is considered known and homogeneous. In this way the constrained surface can be defined as the boundary $\partial\mathcal{O}_c$ of the overlapping spheres \mathcal{O}_c (see fig. 1):

$$\mathcal{O}_c = \bigcup_{\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{O}_s} \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{p}_i\| \leq d_c\}. \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Visualization of a constrained region with overlapping spheres. The red stars denote the set of points \mathcal{O}_s . Blue spheres visualize the activated spheres assuming that the tool tip is in the bottom right angle of the figure.

Furthermore, consider the nearest to the end-effector spheres centered on surface points $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$, as the spheres with its surfaces within a distance $d_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{>0}$ from the end-effector, i.e., the set of the neighboring to the tool sphere centers \mathcal{C} , is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{C} = \{\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{O}_s : \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| \leq (d_0 + d_c)\} \quad (2)$$

Only these spheres will be activated with respect to the active constraints instead of the whole set thus reducing the computational load of the method (fig. 1). In practice, to calculate the set \mathcal{C} , we use the commonly available k -d tree search [26], [27], i.e., we create a k -d tree from the points of \mathcal{O}_s , and we search for all the points close to tool point \mathbf{p} . Parameter d_0 determines the area in which repulsive forces are exerted on the tool point.

The constrained surface $\partial\mathcal{O}_c$ is enforced by the sum of repulsive forces $\mathbf{f}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ produced by the gradient of the function V_i of an Artificial Potential (AP) field:

$$\mathbf{f}_i = -k \frac{\partial V_i}{\partial \mathbf{p}}, \forall \mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C} \quad (3)$$

where $k > 0$ a scalar gain.

The proposed AP function, shown in fig. 2, is the following:

$$V_i = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - \psi_i} \right)^2, \forall \mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\psi_i = \frac{(\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| - (d_0 + d_c))^2}{d_0^2} \quad (5)$$

Remark 1: Notice that $V_i < \infty$ if and only if $\psi_i < 1$. Hence, owing to (2) $\psi_i < 1$ if and only if $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| > d_c$ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The AP function used in this work.

The produced repulsive force of Eq. (3) is therefore given by:

$$\mathbf{f}_i = \frac{2k}{d_0^2(1 - \psi_i)} \ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - \psi_i} \right) \mathbf{e}_i, \forall \mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{e}_i = ((d_0 + d_c) - \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\|) \frac{\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i}{\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\|} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the vector with magnitude the minimum distance between the end-effector tool point and the sphere with direction pointing from center of the sphere towards the tool point.

The proposed AP function (4) has the following properties:

- $V_i(\mathbf{p}) = V(\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\|)$ is a positive continuously differentiable scalar function, for all $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| \in (d_c, d_0 + d_c]$;
- $V_i(\mathbf{p}) \rightarrow \infty$ if only if $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| \rightarrow d_c$;
- $\frac{\partial V_i(\mathbf{p})}{\partial \mathbf{p}}$ is zero if and only if $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| = d_c + d_0$.

Any AP that satisfies the above properties, e.g., the AP function proposed in [28], can be used instead of the proposed AP.

Finally, the total repulsive force on the end-effector, which is utilized as a control signal, is the sum of the \mathbf{f}_i forces produced by each artificial potential field of the neighboring spheres i.e., $\mathbf{f} = \sum_{\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C}} \mathbf{f}_i$.

Remark 2: Notice that the definition of \mathcal{C} in (2) implies that the term $(\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| - (d_0 + d_c))$ in (5) will never be negative, since only surface points that belong in \mathcal{C} are taken into account. Furthermore, any new \mathbf{p}_i entering \mathcal{C} will contribute continuously in \mathbf{f} , as the corresponding repulsive force is initially zero.

Remark 3: Based on the requirement of absence of AC repulsive forces within \mathcal{A} , the value of d_0 is selected as $d_0 = d_m - d_c$ with d_m being the minimum distance between the sets \mathcal{O}_s and \mathcal{A}_s : $d_m = \min\{\|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_a\| : \mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{O}_s, \mathbf{p}_a \in \mathcal{A}_s\}$.

Remark 4: Notice that the approximation of the constraint's surface with spheres can produce ripples in the

repulsive force signal. However, these ripples do not appear in the allowed region and therefore do not hinder the proper execution of the task by the human operator.

C. Stability Analysis

Consider the dynamic model of a 3-dof non-redundant manipulator in the 3-dimensional operational space, with gravity compensation, additive dissipative force and virtual constraint controls under the kinesthetic guidance of a human force:

$$\Lambda_p(\mathbf{p})\ddot{\mathbf{p}} + (\mathbf{C}_p(\mathbf{p}, \dot{\mathbf{p}}) + \mathbf{D}_d)\dot{\mathbf{p}} - \mathbf{u}_c = \mathbf{F}_h, \quad (7)$$

where

$$\Lambda_p(\mathbf{p}) = [\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q})\Lambda^{-1}(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{J}^T(\mathbf{q})]^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_p(\mathbf{p}, \dot{\mathbf{p}})\dot{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{J}^{-T}(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} - \Lambda_p(\mathbf{p})\dot{\mathbf{J}}(\mathbf{q})\dot{\mathbf{q}} \quad (9)$$

with $\mathbf{p}(t), \dot{\mathbf{p}}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the tool tip position and velocity, $\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the robot joint position and velocity, $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ the robot Jacobian, $\mathbf{F}_h \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the human force input to the system, $\Lambda(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ the manipulator's inertia matrix, $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ the Coriolis and centripetal matrix, $\mathbf{D}_d \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ a positive definite matrix of the desired damping and $\mathbf{u}_c = \mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the constraint control signal that is intended to confine the robot position in the constraint-free space $\Omega = \mathbb{R}^3 - \mathcal{O}_c$. Notice that Λ_p is positive definite and the matrix $\Lambda_p - 2\mathbf{C}_p$ is skew symmetric and that the control signal \mathbf{u}_c is enabled while $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \Omega_e \triangleq \bigcup_{\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{O}_s} \{\mathbf{p} \in \Omega : \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| \leq d_c + d_0\}$

In the stability analysis, we investigate the system's output passivity and the system's state boundedness when the external input \mathbf{F}_h is of finite energy. To proceed with the stability analysis, we initially write system (7) in state-space. To this purpose we define $\xi = \sum_{\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C}} V_i(\mathbf{p})$ as an internal system state. Then, utilizing the state vector:

$$\mathbf{s} = [\dot{\mathbf{p}} \ \mathbf{p} \ \xi]^T \in \mathbb{R}^7 \quad (10)$$

we can write system (7) in state-space as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{F}_h), \mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}(t_0) \in D \quad (11)$$

where $D \triangleq \mathbb{R}^3 \times \Omega \times \mathbb{R}$ and

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{F}_h) = \begin{bmatrix} \Lambda_p^{-1}(-(\mathbf{C}_p + \mathbf{D}_d)\dot{\mathbf{p}} + \mathbf{F}_h + \mathbf{u}_c) \\ \dot{\mathbf{p}} \\ (\sum_{\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{\partial V_i}{\partial \mathbf{p}})^T \dot{\mathbf{p}} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Theorem 1: For system (11), the following statements are valid under the exertion of the external human force \mathbf{F}_h :

- 1) As long as $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \Omega_e$
 - a) the system is strictly output passive with respect to the tip velocity $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$,
 - b) the state is bounded and the constrained region is never violated.
- 2) As long as $\mathbf{p} \in \Omega \wedge \mathbf{p} \notin \Omega_e$ the system is globally asymptotically stable for $\mathbf{F}_h = \mathbf{0}$ (0-GAS) and strictly output passive with respect to the tip velocity $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$.

Proof:

1) Let $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \Omega_e$ the space where the active constraint controller is enabled and let $T - t_0$ is the time duration that this is happening. Function $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{F}_h)$ is continuous in t and locally Lipschitz with respect to \mathbf{s} . Owing to Theorem 3.1 of [29], there exists a time instance τ such that the system $\dot{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{F}_h)$ with $\mathbf{s}(t_0) = \mathbf{s}_0 \in D_e \triangleq \mathbb{R}^3 \times \Omega_e \times \mathbb{R}$ has a unique solution in a maximal time interval $[t_0, \tau)$ with $\tau \in (t_0, T]$ i.e., $\mathbf{s}(t) \in D_e$, for all $t \in [t_0, \tau)$.

Let us define the following candidate Lyapunov-like function:

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \Lambda_p \dot{\mathbf{p}} + k \sum_{\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C}} V_i(\mathbf{p}) \geq 0. \quad (12)$$

Taking the time derivative

$$\dot{V} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \dot{\Lambda}_p \dot{\mathbf{p}} + \dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \Lambda_p \ddot{\mathbf{p}} + k \sum_{\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{\partial V_i(\mathbf{p})}{\partial \mathbf{p}} \dot{\mathbf{p}}. \quad (13)$$

Substituting $\Lambda_p \ddot{\mathbf{p}}$ from (7) in (13), and utilizing the skew-symmetry of matrix $(\dot{\Lambda}_p - 2\mathbf{C}_p)$, yields:

$$\dot{V} = -\dot{\mathbf{p}}^T \mathbf{D}_d \dot{\mathbf{p}} + \mathbf{F}_h^T \dot{\mathbf{p}} \leq \mathbf{F}_h^T \dot{\mathbf{p}}, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, \tau). \quad (14)$$

Hence, system (11) is strictly output passive for all $t \in [t_0, \tau)$ (see Definition 6.3 in [29]).

Rewriting (14) by completing the squares, yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} &= -\|\sqrt{\mathbf{D}_d} \dot{\mathbf{p}} - \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\mathbf{D}_d}^{-1} \mathbf{F}_h\|^2 + \frac{1}{4} \mathbf{F}_h^T \mathbf{D}_d^{-1} \mathbf{F}_h \\ &\leq \frac{1}{4} \mathbf{F}_h^T \mathbf{D}_d^{-1} \mathbf{F}_h, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, \tau). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Notice that \mathbf{F}_h represents the force applied by the human to guide the robot. Thus, \mathbf{F}_h is bounded and therefore $\mathbf{F}_h^T \mathbf{D}_d^{-1} \mathbf{F}_h$ is also a bounded function of time. Additionally, the human forces have bounded energy. Hence integrating (15) we get:

$$V \leq V(t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t \frac{1}{4} \mathbf{F}_h^T \mathbf{D}_d^{-1} \mathbf{F}_h < \infty, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, \tau). \quad (16)$$

Thus, ξ and $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$ are bounded under the exertion of human force for all $t \in [t_0, \tau)$ or otherwise there exist compact sets Ω_ξ, Ω_v such that $\xi \in \Omega_\xi \subset \mathbb{R}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{p}} \in \Omega_v \subset \mathbb{R}^3$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau)$. As a consequence, there exists a positive constant $\bar{\varepsilon}_i$ such that: $V_i \leq \bar{\varepsilon}_i$, for all $t \in [t_0, \tau)$, which for the logarithmic function defined in (4) and owing to (2) it yields:

$$0 \leq \psi_i \leq 1 - \frac{1}{e^{\sqrt{2\bar{\varepsilon}_i}}} < 1, \quad \forall t \in [t_0, \tau) \text{ and } i = 1, \dots, M.$$

Hence, following Remark 1 the imposed constraints are not violated. In other words it holds $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| \geq d_1 > d_c$ for all $t \in [t_0, \tau)$ and $i \in \{1, \dots, M\}$. The above analysis is applied when $\mathcal{C} \neq \emptyset$ i.e., when $\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_i\| \leq d_c + d_0$. Thus, \mathbf{p} evolves in Ω_1 , a compact subset of Ω_e and consequently $\mathbf{s}(t) \in D_1 \triangleq \Omega_v \times \Omega_1 \times \Omega_\xi$, a compact subset of D_e for all $t \in [t_0, \tau)$. Using Theorem 3.3 of [29] we can conclude that τ can be extended to T , thus proving the first part of the theorem.

2) When $\mathbf{p} \in \Omega \wedge \mathbf{p} \notin \Omega_e$ then $\mathbf{u}_c = \mathbf{0}$ and (7) takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_p(\mathbf{p}) \dot{\mathbf{v}} + (\mathbf{C}_p(\mathbf{p}, \dot{\mathbf{p}}) + \mathbf{D}_d) \mathbf{v} &= \mathbf{F}_h \\ \dot{\mathbf{p}} &= \mathbf{v}, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where $[\mathbf{v}^T \ \mathbf{p}^T]^T$ is now the system state. When $\mathbf{F}_h = \mathbf{0}$ it is not difficult to verify using the Lyapunov-like function $W = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{v}^T \Lambda_p \mathbf{v}$ that \mathbf{v} converges exponentially to zero. Hence, using Lemma 1 of the Appendix, we can easily conclude that \mathbf{p} converges to a constant. This means that (17) is 0–GAS. Furthermore, it is easy to prove that for $\mathbf{F}_h \neq \mathbf{0}$, $\dot{W} = -\mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{D}_d \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{F}_h \leq \frac{1}{4} \mathbf{F}_h^T \mathbf{D}_d^{-1} \mathbf{F}_h$. Notice that $\mathbf{F}_h^T \mathbf{D}_d^{-1} \mathbf{F}_h$ are bounded functions of time. Thus, following the line of analysis used to prove the 1-part of the theorem, (17) is strictly output passive w.r.t $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$. ■

The above result implies that the robot's end-effector will always remain in the constraint free space Ω and the system will be passive with respect to $\dot{\mathbf{p}}$. In the above analysis it should be stressed that the input $\mathbf{u}_c + \mathbf{F}_h$ when the constrain controller is enable and \mathbf{F}_h when it is disable preserves its continuously as the tool tip enter or leave the field of influence of the active constraint.

D. Extension to the whole tool body

We have extended the above methodology for constraining the whole tool body. We model the tool body as a capsule, thus allowing the analytical computation of the minimum distance from a given point-cloud point. In the case of the whole tool body, the neighboring point-cloud \mathcal{C} is found utilizing an appropriate algorithm [30]. All points $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C}$ have a minimum distance from the capsule surface less than $d_0 + d_c$. For each such point \mathbf{p}_i , the closest point on the capsule \mathbf{p}_{m_i} is computed. The AP field and the respective repulsive forces \mathbf{f}_i is now produced by (3) for $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}_{m_i}$. The total repulsive force \mathbf{f} and torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ induced on the tool body at an appropriately defined position \mathbf{p}_c by the forces \mathbf{f}_i can then be calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{f} = \sum_i \mathbf{f}_i, \quad \boldsymbol{\tau} = \sum_i \mathbf{p}_{cm_i} \times \mathbf{f}_i \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{cm_i} = \mathbf{p}_{m_i} - \mathbf{p}_c$. Under the exertion of the repulsive forces and torques (18) the system is strictly output passive with respect to the generalized velocity and constraint satisfaction is guaranteed. The proof of stability for the enforcement of constraints for the whole tool follows a similar line of analysis to the one given above but in this case a 6-dof non redundant manipulator is involved while the control input is given by the total repulsive force and torque $\mathbf{u}_c = [\mathbf{f}^T, \boldsymbol{\tau}^T]^T$ calculated from (18).

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology, a user physically guides a 7-dof KUKA LWR4+ robotic manipulator acting as a master device to a virtual slave scene consisted of an identical virtual manipulator and the point cloud of a kidney and its surrounding vessels that

have been characterised as forbidden areas (see fig. 3). The master joint positions are given to the virtual KUKA and the repulsive generalized force that may be generated at the virtual scene is applied to the master tool tip and felt by the user. The proposed methodology is implemented in C++ using the FRI library with control frequency $f_s = 500$ Hz. The virtual slave scene is visualized utilizing Rviz embedded in ROS framework. Both the force exerted by the user and the repulsive force felt at the master's wrist are also visualized in the scene. To visualize the exerted force, a wrist force/torque sensor (ATI Mini40) is utilized to measure it at the master device. Notice that the measurement of the exerted force is not needed in the control scheme, its main purpose being its visualization. The user guides the slave tool via the master close to the point cloud by observing the slave scene. This experiment emulates the use case of robot-assisted partial nephrectomy in which the allowed area is a human kidney and the area to be avoided by the tool body is the surrounding vessels (fig. 4a). In the real case the 3D point cloud of the surgical site will be provided by the endoscopic camera and the characterization of the forbidden areas can be performed by the surgeon via a friendly human machine interface.

Fig. 3. The experimental set up consisting of the master KUKA and the virtual surgical scene with the KUKA slave and the organ's point cloud.

A virtual tool is modeled as a capsule with radius $r = 0.009m$ and length $l = 0.08m$ and extends beyond the actual tool to simulate the scalpel blade (fig. 5).

Fig. 4. (a) Visualization of the point cloud of a kidney (green) and its surrounding vessels (red) \mathcal{O}_s (b) Visualization of the constraint surface $\partial\mathcal{O}_c$ with the overlapping spheres centered at the points of the zoom area (yellow circle).

Fig. 5. The virtual tool modeled as a red capsule.

The distance d_0 for the activation of the repulsive force, is set to a prefixed value $d_0 = 2.3$ cm. This implies that the operator will start to feel forces when the virtual tool is at a distance from the vessels less than $d_0 + d_c = 2.301768$ cm. The controller gain is set to the value $k = 0.006$. Initially the point cloud of the vessels is downsampled to increase computational performance and the radius of the spheres to cover the empty spaces is calculated to the value of $d_c = 1.768$ mm (fig. 4b). This implies that the virtual tool can only be guided at distances greater than 1.768 mm from the vessels. In order to account for point cloud density variations a normalization of the repulsive force and torque signal is performed for the implementation. Such a solution for the force was suggested in [24]. In fact we have used:

$$\mathbf{f} = \frac{\max(\mathbf{f}_i) \sum_i \mathbf{f}_i}{\|\sum_i \mathbf{f}_i\|}, \tau = \frac{\max(\|\mathbf{f}_i\|) \sum_i \mathbf{p}_{cm_i} \times \mathbf{f}_i}{\|\sum_i \mathbf{f}_i\|}. \quad (19)$$

In the experiment, the human operator was asked to try to guide the tool initially on the kidney (fig. 6a) and then approach the constrained region (vessels) (fig. 6b, 6c). As he moves towards the vessels, the centers of the spheres within the selected threshold d_0 are found (blue area) and start to produce repulsive forces (fig. 6b) which get bigger as he moves closer to the vessels (fig. 6c). Thus the operator fails to penetrate the constrained region which is kept safe. Fig. 7 depicts the measured minimum distance of the virtual tool (red capsule in fig. 6) from the points $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C}$, the norm of the repulsive force and the respective torque. The smaller the minimum distance, the larger the repulsive force by the controller (see for eg around the 8th and 15th second), while the torque depends on the tool's approaching direction and can be small even in small distances when the torques from the repulsive torques partially cancel out (see around the 15th second and fig. 6c for such an example). In these experimental results, repulsive forces in the region of 10N have been exerted before the user moved away from the forbidden areas. Experiments with a couple of other users indicated that this magnitude of haptic feedback was sufficient to discourage him from moving closer to the sensitive areas.

IV. CONCLUSION

A constraint enforcement controller is proposed to guarantee that the robot tool will never touch a constraint surface modeled by a point cloud. The proposed approach utilizes Artificial Potential fields to produce repulsive wrenches on the tool in the vicinity of the constraints. The controlled system under the exertion of a human force is proved to be

Fig. 6. Experiment with the free-to-move region of a kidney (green) and the constrained region of human vessels (red). With purple arrow the force exerted by the operator on the robot, with yellow arrow the repulsive force \mathbf{f} of the controller, sensed by the human, with blue points the points $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathcal{C}$ and with yellow points the respective points \mathbf{p}_m on the capsule surface. (a) The operator moves along the area of the kidney, where no repulsive force is generated. (b) The operator moves the robot close to vessels starting to feel the resistance of the repulsive force. (c) The operator moves towards the vessels and fails to violate the active constraint due to the repulsive forces.

Fig. 7. The minimum distance of the capsule from the points on the constrained region surface, the norm of the repulsive force and the respective torque during the experiment with the region of the kidney and the adjacent vessels.

strictly output passive with respect to the end-effector velocity and is confined in the constraint free space. Experimental results for the whole tool are given in a scenario emulating partial nephrectomy utilizing a KUKA LWR4+ acting as a master device and a virtual slave scene consisted of an identical virtual manipulator and the point cloud of a kidney and its surrounding vessels. Experimental results demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed scheme. In our future work we will investigate and validate the proposed controller in a real master-slave setup with a phantom organ.

APPENDIX

A. Convergence

Lemma 1: Suppose $\mathbf{b} : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^w$ and satisfies $0 \leq \|\mathbf{b}(t)\| \leq ne^{-\lambda t}$, for all $t \in [0, \infty)$ where $n, \lambda > 0$. Then $\int_0^\infty \mathbf{b}(t)dt$ converges to a constant.

Proof: As $0 \leq \|\mathbf{b}(t)\| \leq ne^{-\lambda t}$, for all $t \in [0, \infty)$ and $\int_0^\infty ne^{-\lambda t} dt$ converges to a constant, by the direct

comparison test¹ we obtain that $\int_0^\infty \|\mathbf{b}(t)\| dt$ is convergent to a constant. Further, let $b_i(t)$ denoting the i -th element of the $\mathbf{b}(t)$ vector. Then $0 \leq |b_i(t)| \leq \|\mathbf{b}(t)\|$; thus using again the direct comparison test we obtain that $\int_0^\infty |b_i(t)| dt$ is convergent to a constant. However, if an improper integral converges absolutely then it converges [32]. Hence, $\int_0^\infty b_i(t) dt$ converges to a constant and therefore $\int_0^\infty \mathbf{b}(t) dt$ converges to a constant as well. ■

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¹If $0 \leq z(t) \leq c(t)$ for all $t \in [0, \infty)$ and $\int_0^\infty c(t) dt$ converges to a constant then $\int_0^\infty z(t) dt$ converges to a constant [31].

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